

MARINEWIND

Market Uptake Measures of Floating Offshore Wind Technology Systems (FOWTs)

1/11/2022 – 31/10/2025

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T1.3_Greek Lab 1st Co-creation Workshop Report

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1 EVENT DETAILS

EVENT LOCATION: Yacht Club of Greece, 18 Karagiorgi Servias, 18533, Piraeus, Greece.

EVENT DATE: Thursday, 19 October 2023 (4 hours, co-creation session: 45 minutes)

EVENT TITLE: Offshore renewable energy Greece / MARINEWIND European project: Co-creation Path to Awareness on Floating Offshore Wind Technology Systems (FOWTs)

TYPE OF EVENT: Physical

CATEGORY OF THE EVENT: Co-creation Workshop

EVENT AFFILIATION: Offshore Renewable Energy Greece, Official Partner of the EMD – European Maritime Day 2023

19 OCTOBER
2023
Athens

Offshore
renewable energy
Greece

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LEAD ORGANISER: Q-PLAN International

LANGUAGE: English

CONCEPT:

The MARINEWIND co-creation workshop aimed to bring together different Greek and international stakeholders interested in the developments of Offshore wind in Greece, in order to discuss and explore the potential of the Floating Offshore Wind Technologies (FOWTs) in Greece. The workshop was part of the 1st Offshore Renewable Energy Greece event and took place in Athens, where most of

the industrial stakeholders are located. The targeted event was a great opportunity to gather great audience from all the different key stakeholders, mainly industrial actors, in order to discuss the developments on the Offshore Wind Market in Greece and fostering potential synergies for the development of OWFs in the upcoming period.

More specifically, the workshop session aimed to inform the participants about the MARINEWIND project and identify the most critical barriers and enablers for the investment on FOWTs in Greece through a co-creation session. The participants were actively participated in the co-creation session, sharing their knowledge and expertise, and expressed their views on what is needed in order to accelerate the commercialisation and deployment of FOWTs, not only for Greece but also in Europe.

OBJECTIVES

- Increase awareness on FOWTs via co-creation activities that directly engage policy and decision makers, market and business actors, civil society organisations and funding bodies.
- Identify critical barriers and enablers on FOWTs in order to accelerate the investment and commercialization these technologies.
- Increase Social acceptance on FOWTs facilities and installations by directly involving local communities and citizens and by addressing potential environmental issues.
- Facilitate communication and collaboration among all the stakeholders directly and indirectly involved in Greek MARINEWIND Lab.

TARGET AUDIENCE:

Following the Quintuple Helix approach, the event targeted mainly industrial stakeholders, research and academia representatives, green innovators, civil society actors and representatives of public authorities, directly involved in the Greek Lab. For each specific category, the involved actors were:

- **Industry:** FOWT installation developers, engineering companies, tech/project developers, trade associations (fisheries and tourism).
- **Academia:** Scientific & Research Community.
- **Public authorities:** National (Ministries for Energy & Infrastructure, for Industry and Environment, Regulatory authority for energy, Hydrocarbons and Energy Resources Management Company) and local level (Regional authorities), maritime transport authorities, policymakers.
- **Civil society:** NGOs, civil society organisations, and citizens.
- **Green innovation:** SMEs, public/private financial investors, insurers, ecologists, environmental organisations, and natural parks.

In addition, the event targeted also actors and key stakeholders from offshore wind sector in France due to the support of the conference from the French Maritime Cluster and the Greco-French commercial and industrial foundation.

PARTICIPANTS OF YOUR EVENT: 120 participants

Figure 1: Participants overview

2 OVERVIEW OF CONTRIBUTIONS AND INTERVENTIONS BY THE SPEAKERS

2.1 The potential of offshore wind energy in Greece

The opening session of the event started with a thorough overview of the challenges, opportunities and perspectives on offshore wind in Greece, by the CEO of FARIA Renewables, Thalia Valkouma. The most critical challenges defined for the offshore wind in Greece are summarised in Table 1.

Table 1: Offshore wind challenges in Greece

<p>Commercial & Financial challenges</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Inflation - Increased capital cost ○ Lack of experience in the local banking sector ○ Supply chain crisis ○ Race-to-the-bottom pricing schemes 	<p>Technical challenges</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Scale up quickly to industrial size projects ○ Steep learning curve for bottom fixed projects and ride global floating wind wave ○ Unexplored seabed compared to other markets (North Sea, Baltic Sea) ○ Infrastructure challenge – reinforcements required for Grid, Shipyards and Ports – Local Content
<p>Regulatory challenges</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Stable OW specific legal framework to attract investors and establish Greek as an elite offshore market for Tier 1 investors ○ Compatibility with national Marine Spatial Planning to avoid conflict between sea users ○ Clearly communicated long term OW installation targets to gauge developers' and supply chain appetite ○ Permitting framework to be tailored to OW individualities and timelines to be rationalised. Avoid inadequate and inefficient permitting and licensing rules 	<p>Social challenges</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Address lack of information and education. Communicate and cooperate efficiently with local communities and other stakeholders. ○ Assess carefully potential effects and apply mitigation measures ○ Offer of remunerative measures to the communities that will host the projects ○ Enhance local growth

In addition, a number of critical issues highlighted while trying to deliver the big ambitions of offshore wind in Greece. Some of the most important issues are summarized below:

- The Commercial Banking system should start preparing for the sector, designing financing tools and supplementary facilities that could be used by the investors to mitigate risk.
- A clear and efficient permitting process shall be in place and be administered by a competent and trusted entity.
- Stakeholder management in all the areas selected for offshore wind development shall start immediately. Everyone has to be clearly informed and not to be left to misinformation.
- Mitigation measures and compensatory measures should start to be planned and discussed and go under consultation with those stakeholders involved.

- Investments in local marine infrastructure (shipyards and ports) shall take place early. Government can play a key role in incentivizing and promoting this activity the soonest possible.
- Collaboration with international experienced supply chain leaders for experience transfer and knowledge sharing.
- Plan ahead and long term and secure timely grid connection for planned OW projects, according to the selected areas in first and following cycles.

The opening session ended with poly insights from, Efi Karra - Sustainability & Policy Advocacy Officer from Hellenic Wind Energy Association (HWEA), who provided a strategic overview of the prospects and the challenges for Offshore Wind sector in Greece, its benefits and added value for Greece and more specifically for Greek economy as well as the relevant efforts and initiatives of HWEA the previous years.

2.2 What are the needs of a wind farm at early-stage development?

The next session of the event focused on the actual needs at the early stages of a wind farm construction. The first speaker Ben Oudman – Head of Offshore Wind at DNV, provided a detailed overview of the energy transition outlook, focusing on the bankability of the floating wind projects during the feasibility phase and what are the challenges as well as the critical risks to overcome in order to make a floating project bankable. The figure below describes the main risks, the mitigation measures and the necessary tools to avoid those risks according to DNV.

Risks	Consequence categories	Mitigation	Tool
Site conditions <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Wind (meteocean) measurement campaigns not properly conducted – EPA not bankable • Lack of good geotech seabed and environmental data – foundations, cable trenches and env. permitting 		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Proper measurement campaign, designed and quality controlled by independent technical advisor 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Campaign design • FLIDAR validation • Data validation • JMC's
Supply and inst. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Bankable floater & station keeping technologies • Set contingency & project reserves 		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Bankability risk identification & mitigation of technologies • Project QRA's, incl. liquidated damages & stress tests 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Bankability report • PQRA's
O&M <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Unproven technology impacting insurance premium and limiting coverage • Inadequate strategy for O&M of Wind Turbine Generators and Balance of Plant 		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Qualify unproven technological solutions • Perform project specific O&M strategy modelling 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Technology Qualification • O&M strategy modelling tool
Transmission /Grid <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Grid availability and connection timeline and associated permits • Transmission and Grid outages due to failures 		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Grid availability assessment and close interaction with grid operator 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Grid studies and expected timelines
Supply chain <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Inexperience of the local supply chain with offshore wind leading to quality issues • Readiness level of local supply chain such as ports, fabrication and marshalling yards 		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Assess supply chain in early stage and consider independent quality control and inspections strategy 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Supply chain assessment, QA/QC, inspect. by independent party

Figure 2: Critical risks ensuring bankability of a (floating) offshore wind project (source: DNV)

The next speaker of the session Elvira Aliverdieva – Product & Offering Specialist at Vaisala, provided useful information on how wind lidar is meeting the challenges of offshore wind measurements and reduce the uncertainties over the entire wind (and solar) farm lifecycle. More specifically, Elvira presented several lidar solutions to address offshore Wind Resource Assessment, from floating lidar systems, dual scanning lidar systems and combination of the above.

Mathieu Daden – Sales Manager at Akrocean, stressed the importance of reliable data collection technologies for: a) energy yield assessment, b) required support investment and financing decisions and c) accurate site resource assessment. Mathieu presented the advantages of the floating lidar to be used for offshore wind projects.

The next speaker, Thibaut Debouche – General manager at G-Tec, provided an analytical overview of the needs at early-stage development of an offshore wind farm construction, focusing on intelligent site investigations in order to provide actionable insights to maximize the value of data collected.

The next speaker, Pauline Oien – Head of Commercial at Vind AI, raised the importance of wind development while mitigating the impact on nature and local societies. According to Pauline, there is an increase of non-price criteria in European auctions. 30% of the criteria in European auctions focus on a) biodiversity, b) local interests, c) local suppliers, d) sustainability, and e) other options, making clear that there is a need to follow an iterative, holistic process of working to find the best solution for establishing an offshore wind project.

Finally, the last speaker of that session, Ramsey Nehme – Head of project development Europe at SBM offshore, showcased the Provence Grand Large Floating Offshore Wind Pilot Project, the 1st floating offshore wind farm in France and the 1st in the world using Tension Leg Platform (TLP) technology. In addition, Ramsey provided useful information about scaling up from pilot projects to large commercial wind farms, describing the key factors for successful project execution.

2.3 Return on experience on Saint-Nazaire Offshore Wind Farm

The last presentation was given by Alexandre Veniamin – BU Manager South EU at DEME Offshore Renewable and focused on Saint-Nazaire Offshore wind project. Alexandre showcased the overall project along with its challenges, technical innovations and the logistics and local content that influence the development of the project. One of the most important findings was the fact that 200 direct suppliers from France were involved to the offshore wind project, 80% were SMEs thus showing the significant benefits of the local supply chain from such projects.

3 ROUNDTABLES TOPICS OVERVIEW

3.1 Supporting the growth, what are the main challenges?

Following the talks from the various keynote speakers, a panel discussion about the main challenges in the growth of the offshore wind in Greece took place. The discussion moderated by Eleni Tsirikou – Sustainability strategy & business development at Intec and three key stakeholders were at the discussion panel, namely: Panos Bafis – Hydrogen and Business Development at FARIA Renewables, Philippe Leon – EOLE Project Manager at Nantes Saint-Nazaire Port and Vasilis Giotas – Country Manager Greece at OWC.

The main focus of the discussion was about the environmental and social benefits of the offshore wind farms. The debate on how to increase the social acceptance of the offshore wind farms brought up

several key points. It was noted that people directly interested in such topics (civil society, fishermen associations, etc) are not usually invited to speak for these issues, so they believe that no one will ever listen to and understand their concerns.

The discussion also highlighted the need for renewable companies to become more extrovert and analytically inform the society about the generated income for the local economy from the development of such projects. The example of Tilos island, was given as the 1st energy autonomous island in Greece.

In addition, social pressure could be avoided by having better communication about the benefits for the local community, either in economic or environmental. Finally, education and awareness about the advantages of offshore wind farms could have positive impact on reducing the negative perceptions based mainly on ignorance.

4 CO-CREATION ACTIVITIES

One of the main activities of the event was the workshop with the co-creation session in order to interact with the audience of the conference. For that reason, a survey on the MENTIMETER online tool was prepared by APRE, adapted by Q-PLAN and shared to the participants in order to collect useful information. It is common in such co-creation activities that some of the event participants didn't join the online tool.

The official results along with the number of individual responses, as drawn from the MENTIMETER Tool, are presented in Annex I.

4.1 Question 1: Types of organisations represented

The attendees participated in the co-creation activities were mostly industry oriented, covering a large variety of technology providers, engineering companies and offshore wind project developers. In addition, there was adequate participation from research and academia representatives, green innovation stakeholders, public authorities and civil society actors. Finally, many of the participants (13) chose the "other" option meaning that they categorize themselves in a different category. In total, 60 participants were actively engaged in the co-creation activities as indicated in Figure 3.

Figure 3: Type of organisations involved

4.2 Question 2: Key enabling factors to invest in FOWTs

For this question, the participants were asked to select up to three options from the provided list about the key enabling factors to invest in FOWTs, in Greece. Based on their responses, the most critical enabling factors were the clear regulatory framework, following by the potential for development of the local supply chain. Very close in total responses was the need for technological maturity, followed by the stability of the national transmission grid. The remaining options seem to be less significant, at least in the initial development phase of the offshore wind sector in Greece.

Figure 4: Key enabling factors to invest in FOWTs

4.3 Question 3: Most significant risk in the supply chain

Concerning the risks associated with the supply chain, the participants highlighted as most significant, by far, the development of adequate infrastructure which reflects the fact that there is no adequate port infrastructure to deal with the offshore wind turbines in Greece. The next concern of the participants was the capacity of the supply chain at the local level, identifying potential difficulties in adapting to increased capacities from the local suppliers. All responses are summarized in Figure 5.

Figure 5: Significant risks in Supply Chain for floating offshore wind

4.4 Question 4: Deployment of FOWTs while respecting other sea uses

The next question was searching for the aspects which could sustainably encourage the deployment of FOWTs while respecting other uses. The most popular response was the long-term planning, followed by the development of more eco-friendly technologies for the marine environment. In addition, the improved regulatory framework in Greece was selected by 8 participants, while the incentives for local communities and the compatibility with tourist vocation of many maritime areas were the least selected responses.

Figure 6: Aspects on deployment of FOWTs while respecting other uses

4.5 Question 5: Sea uses to be considered in planning the diffusion of offshore wind

In the open question about which other sea uses should be considered in planning the diffusion of offshore wind in Greece, we received 59 responses in total. Almost all the participants highlighted that fishing, tourism and navigation should be taken into consideration. In addition, defense is also considered as a very important sea use, taken into account the specificities with the neighboring countries in Greece. Other choices of the participants were aquaculture, wave and solar energy, hydrocarbon activities and other human activities (bird monitoring, scuba diving, watersports etc.). Some indicative responses can be found in Figure 7.

Navigation	Fishing	Maritime industry
Shipping	Fishing, tourism	Tourism, Public opinion, defense and security
Marine shelter; Fishing Breeding ground	Navigation, defense	Tourism

Figure 7: Sea uses to be considered in planning Offshore wind

Figure 9: Activities in conflict with the offshore wind sector in Greece

5 SUMMARY OF IDENTIFIED BARRIERS AND ENABLERS

The 1st of the three co-creation workshops for T1.3 with regards to the Greek Lab has been mainly dedicated to barriers perceived by the stakeholders for the investment on FOWTs, and to potential enablers. Thanks to the data collected, the next two workshops will then focus on solutions and policies to ease the installation of Offshore Wind Plants. The table below summarises the main barriers, criticalities and bottlenecks identified during the workshop on one side, and the most significant enablers and incentives on the other.

BARRIERS	ENABLERS
<p>Regulatory framework stability The regulatory framework and the bureaucratic procedures caused by the different responsible public bodies (Ministries, HEREMA, Independent Power Transmission Operator (IPTO), and the Regulatory Authority for Energy (RAE)) can result in significant delays which could discourage potential investors.</p>	<p>Ideal depth of the Greek seas The depths of the Greek seas are ideal for the rapid development of Floating Offshore Wind projects.</p>
<p>Significant uncertainty in the market There is an overall uncertainty in the market of renewables around the globe which affects also the Greek market thus creating barriers in accelerating the floating offshore wind projects. There are no specific answers about increased</p>	<p>Robust regulatory framework Significant effort of the Greek state to establish a robust and stable national regulatory framework for the Offshore Wind Development in Greece from HEREMA.</p>

capacity of electricity grid or potential storage infrastructures.	
<p>Increased costs across supply chain</p> <p>The rapid increase of the prices of the commodities across the entire supply chain are affecting the viability of offshore wind projects and are currently barriers on the investments on FOWTs.</p>	<p>International cooperations between companies</p> <p>Joint ventures between Greek and international companies which have significant experience in development and operation of offshore wind projects.</p>
<p>Current limitations in local supply chain</p> <p>For the successful implementation of the offshore wind projects in Greece, there should be great upgrades in the local supply chain in which there are significant limitations in almost all crucial supply chain activities.</p>	<p>Policy support</p> <p>Significant economic incentives and advantages at local level can act as an enabler for investments in FOWTs.</p>
<p>Lack of integrated Maritime Spatial Planning</p> <p>The lack of an integrated Maritime Spatial Planning in Greece is highlighted as a barrier on potential investments on offshore wind projects in Greece.</p>	<p>Long-term EU policy on Offshore Wind sector</p> <p>Stability on behalf of national government and the European Union regarding the energy policy and the perception that the floating offshore wind projects are the next big thing in renewable energy sector.</p>
<p>Locations for Offshore Wind Projects are limited to 6 nautical miles</p> <p>The impossibility of selecting areas beyond 6 nautical miles due to relations with neighboring countries for offshore wind projects is a barrier for investments on FOWTs in Greece.</p>	<p>Experience in grid connection challenges</p> <p>There is significant experience and expertise in electricity grid interconnection projects from national companies which can act as enabler for potential investors.</p>
<p>Social acceptance of the Offshore Wind Farms</p> <p>There is a general opposition on the wind energy developments (onshore & offshore) in Greece which can cause significant delays in the construction phase put in jeopardy the economic viability of the projects.</p>	

6 ANNEX I – MENTIMETER TOOL RESULTS

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Which industry are you representing? (1/7)

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What are the key enabling factors to invest in FOWTs? (up to 3 answers) (2/7)

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Where is the most significant risk in your supply chain? (3/7)

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What aspects could sustainably encourage the deployment of FOWTs while respecting other sea uses? (4/7)

What other sea uses should be considered in planning the diffusion of offshore wind? (5/7)

Aquaculture	Fishing	Navigation	Fishing
Tourism	Fishing and military	Defense	Fishing

What other sea uses should be considered in planning the diffusion of offshore wind? (5/7)

Fishing	Fishing	Navigation, defence, tourism, fishing	Watersports
Fishing	Fishing	Fishery, aquaculture	Tourism, navigation

What other sea uses should be considered in planning the diffusion of offshore wind? (5/7)

Wave energy	Wave energy	fishing	Fishing
Marine traffic, fishing, tourism	Bird monitoring	Fishing	Fishing, aquaculture

What other sea uses should be considered in planning the diffusion of offshore wind? (5/7)

Fishing	Biodiversity and fishing	Aquaculture and fishing	Fishing, sailing,
Cross sector use	Solar	Fishing	Navy operations

What other sea uses should be considered in planning the diffusion of offshore wind? (5/7)

Scientific researches	Fisheries	Aquaculture	Maritime routes
Navigation	Fishing	Maritime industry	Shipping

What other sea uses should be considered in planning the diffusion of offshore wind? (5/7)

Fishing, tourism	Tourism, Public opinion, defense and security	Marine shelter, Fishing, Breeding ground	Navigation, defense
Tourism	Fishing and military	Security, fishing, aquaculture	Offshore platforms

What other sea uses should be considered in planning the diffusion of offshore wind? (5/7)

Scuba diving	Tourism	Nature like design	Shipping routes, tourism
Oil&Gas	Fishing Marine protected areas	vessel navigation, fishing, Aqua eco systems	Marine traffics and marine spwceoccupancies.

What other sea uses should be considered in planning the diffusion of offshore wind? (5/7)

Fishing, tourism, navigation routes, pipelines, hydrocarbons,

fishing, navigation, eco systems

Maritime transport mainly (dense coastal shipping network) but also fishing

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Which activity is most in conflict with the offshore wind sector? (7/7)

